

1 **Identification And Quantification of Odorous Compounds From Adhesives Used In**
2 **Food Packaging Materials By Headspace Solid Phase Extraction And Headspace**
3 **Solid Phase Microextraction Coupled To Gas Chromatography Olfactometry Mass**
4 **Spectrometry.**

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13 Adhesives, food packaging, odor, GC-O-MS, D-GC-O, paper, odor analysis

14 **Abstract.**

15 Adhesives are often responsible for off-flavors in food in contact with packaging. The
16 aim of this investigation was to identify by GC-O-MS the odorous compounds in five
17 different types of adhesive (hotmelt, vinyl acetate ethylene, starch, polyvinyl acetate and
18 acrylic) used in food packaging. In order to obtain a substantial number of compounds,
19 they were extracted by two complementary extraction methods: HS-SPE and HS-SPME.
20 Fifteen minutes extraction time using PDMS fiber for hotmelt adhesive and
21 DVD/CAR/PDMS fiber for the other adhesives were the best conditions for defining a
22 representative solvent-free adhesive extract using a rapid and simple D-GC-O technique.
23 Thirty three compounds were identified by GC-O-MS. These include butyric acid, acetic
24 acid, methyl butyrate, 1-butanol and nonanal, which were present in most of the adhesives
25 under study producing cheesy, rancid, sour, medicinal and green aromas, respectively.
26 The concentrations were determined, the most abundant compound being acetic acid with
27 concentrations from 22.9 to 8,930 µg/g of adhesive.

28

29 **1. Introduction**

30 Adhesives are commonly used in multilayer materials for food packaging. In most
31 applications, although they are not in direct contact with the food, their constituents can
32 migrate through the multilayer materials and contaminate it [1,2] as has already been
33 shown in previous studies [3-5].

34 Packaging materials can also contain a large number of compounds responsible for off-
35 flavors deriving from the degradation of the materials or the manufacturing process,
36 including printing, coating and lamination. Off-flavors are also produced by the
37 interaction between food and packaging. These off-flavors can modify the organoleptic
38 properties of food and produce a negative effect on the quality of the product [6-13]. For
39 food companies, this can lead to an increase in production costs or a possible loss of brand
40 confidence and market share.

41 Traditionally, the control of odors in the packaging and food industries has been carried
42 out by a trained panel. However, this technique is not valid for identifying the individual
43 compounds responsible for odors and thus for correcting and eliminating the problem
44 [14]. Only an overall perception of the odor and the absence or presence of undesired
45 odors can be detected by a panel. The electronic nose, which is an attractive tool for the
46 quality control of odors, only allows a comparison of the odor response of a sample to
47 that obtained from a reference sample. It can identify neither the odor nor the individual
48 compound responsible for it. Gas chromatography – olfactometry (GC-O) includes a
49 sniffing port in which the human nose acts as an odor detector. When this device is
50 combined with GC-MS, the system as a whole becomes a powerful tool for identifying
51 the individual compound responsible for an odor. This technique was proposed by Fuller
52 et al. [15], where successful detection of active compounds was achieved by sniffing the
53 effluent during gas chromatography. This methodology has proved to be a valuable
54 method for the selection of odor active compounds from a complex mixture, as the human
55 nose is a much more sensitive detector than the conventional “chemical” detectors for
56 such compounds which can be present in very low concentrations [16]. Using this
57 technique, it is common to have very different profiles of odor active compounds than
58 those of the chemical compounds registered in the chromatogram. The odorants
59 frequently provide a higher signal than the non-odorants because of the higher sensitivity
60 of the human nose compared to instrumental detectors.

61 Although this technique has been used for identifying the aroma-producing compounds
62 in many types of foodstuffs, including wine and spirits, their identification in food
63 packaging materials and specifically the influence of adhesives contained in them has not

64 yet been tackled. This is surprising given that companies producing packaging materials
65 are obliged to exercise control over these materials which can spoil packaged food and
66 cause serious complaints from customers and consumers. Even though this issue is
67 usually more closely related to food quality than safety, it should be remembered that
68 consumer perception of odors is perhaps one of the main reasons for complaints.
69 Within the framework of packaging materials, adhesives constitute an important source
70 of chemicals. Formulas specifically developed to glue different materials together in an
71 efficient manner contain many different substances. As adhesives are not usually in direct
72 contact with food, their contribution to the quality and safety packaged food has not been
73 adequately explored. There is no European legislation concerning adhesives in contact
74 with food and thus very few studies of adhesives have appeared in the literature in the last
75 five years. The European Research Project MIGRESIVES provided a considerable
76 amount of information concerning different types of adhesives and their contribution to
77 migration to food, but no mention was made of off-flavors or odorant compounds that
78 can migrate to food. The main objective of this paper, therefore, is to study the
79 contribution of several adhesives to off-flavors present in several packaging materials,
80 and to provide appropriate protocols for the identification by GC-O-MS of the odorous
81 compounds in different types of adhesives used in a series of multilayer packaging
82 materials. For this purpose, several analytical and sensory techniques have been
83 developed, applied and validated using a wide variety of adhesives and samples. The
84 results obtained are shown and discussed.

85

86 **2. Materials and methods**

87 *2.1. Reagents*

88 The standards 1-butanol (71-36-3), p-xylene (106-42-3), p-cymene (99-87-6), nonanal
89 (124-19-6), propanoic acid (79-09-4), naphthalene (91-20-3), benzaldehyde (100-52-7),
90 toluene (108-88-3), hexanal (66-25-1), paraldehyde (123-63-7), butyl acrylate (141-32-
91 2), 1-hexanol (111-27-3), cyclohexanol (108-93-0), methyl benzoate (93-58-3), allyl
92 benzoate (583-04-0), butyric acid (107-92-6), methyl butyrate (623-42-7), acetic acid (64-
93 19-4), ethyl acetate (141-78-6), methyl methacrylate (80-62-6), butyl propanoate (590-
94 01-2), styrene (100-42-5), 2-octanone (111-13-7), 2-ethylhexyl acetate (103-09-3), 2-
95 ethyl-1-hexanol (104-76-7), camphor (76-22-2), 1-octanol (111-87-5) and 4-tert-
96 butylphenol (98-54-4) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Química S.A (Madrid,
97 Spain). All were of analytical quality. Dichloromethane and acetic acid, both of HPLC

98 grade, were supplied by Scharlau Chemie S.A (Sentmenat, Spain). An alkane standard
99 solution C8-C20 at 40 µg/g in hexane was used to calculate retention indexes. A solution
100 of 4-tert-butylphenol at 1000 µg/g in methanol was used as an internal standard solution.
101 The SPME fibers were supplied by Supelco (Bellefonte, PA, USA).

102

103 2.2. Adhesive samples and laminates.

104 Different types of adhesives commonly used in food packaging were obtained: three vinyl
105 acetate ethylene (VAE) adhesives, three hotmelt (HM), one starch, one acrylic (ACR) and
106 one polyvinyl acetate (PVA).

107 All the adhesives were water based with the exception of the HM. The VAE_01 and PVA
108 adhesives contained triacetin as a plasticizer, while the VAE_02 and VAE_03 adhesives
109 were manufactured with diethylene glycol dibenzoate as a plasticizer. Tackifiers and an
110 antioxidant were present in the starch and acrylic adhesives, but details of their formulas
111 cannot be given for reasons of confidentiality.

112 Three hotmelt adhesives were supplied. Hotmelt 1 (HM1) was based on ethylene vinyl
113 acetate (EVA) and hotmelt 2 (HM2) on a polyolefin enriched with propene. No precise
114 information was provided for hotmelt 3. These adhesives are solid polymers (films,
115 granules or pellets) at room temperature. To manufacture the laminates, the hotmelt
116 adhesives are first heated at 160-180 °C. Once melted, they are applied and extended on
117 a substrate forming a uniform layer. Afterwards, a second substrate is placed on this
118 surface and some pressure is applied to form the laminate. For this study, the hotmelt
119 adhesives were heated at 160°C until they were melted and they were then applied on a
120 flat surface (silicone paper) and cooled to room temperature, simulating the cured process.
121 For the selection of the most odorant adhesive, the hotmelt and VAE adhesives were also
122 studied as part of multilayer laminates. The laminates were market samples provided by
123 different European companies with the structure [Cardboard (CB)–adhesive–Cardboard
124 (CB)]. Most were not printed and were manufactured with different amounts of adhesive
125 per m² of laminate. The substrates used for their manufacture were also separately
126 provided and were of different grammage and thickness. The laminates studied were as
127 follows:

- 128 • Lam_01: CB (350 g/m² and 502 µm) - VAE_01 (31.8 g_{adhesive}/m² laminate) - CB
- 129 • Lam_02: CB (350 g/m² and 479 µm) - VAE_02 (49.1 g_{adhesive}/m² laminate) - CB
- 130 • Lam_03: CB (300 g/m² and 485 µm) - VAE_03 (30.7 g_{adhesive}/m² laminate) - CB

- 131 • Lam_04: CB (380 g/m² and 380 μm) - HM_01 (31.3 g_{adhesive}/m² laminate) - CB
- 132 • Lam_05: CB (380 g/ m² and 380 μm)- HM_02 (31.3 g_{adhesive}/m² laminate) - CB
- 133 • Lam_06: CB (400 g/ m² and 570 μm)- HM_03 (68.2 g_{adhesive}/m² laminate) - CB

134 CB signifies cardboard, HM hotmelt and VAE vinyl acetate ethylene.

135 For the rest of the work, the adhesives were individually studied.

136

137 *2.3. Selection of the most odorant adhesives and their sensory analysis.*

138 The main objective of this work was the identification of the odorous compounds within
139 each type of adhesive. As several hotmelt and VAE adhesives were available, the most
140 odorous adhesive within each group of hotmelt and VAE were initially selected by a
141 triangular test. Three products were shown to the assessors of which two were identical
142 and one was different. The assessors were asked to distinguish which product they
143 believed was the odd one out.

144 The triangular test was carried out with the laminates described above (Lam_01, Lam_02,
145 Lam_03, Lam_04, Lam_05 and Lam_06) as manufactured (CB-adhesive-CB) and the
146 different substrates without the adhesive used to produce each laminate.

147 It consisted of finding the different odorous vial among three vials containing 1*5cm² of
148 laminate or substrate cut into strips. This difference depends on the odorant capacity of
149 each adhesive.

150 For this purpose, one panel formed by 20 panelists, previously trained with adhesive
151 odors, was asked to identify the different vial from among three colourless vials (capacity
152 70 mL) where either one vial or two contained 1*5 cm² of laminate cut into strips and
153 two vials or one contained two substrates with the same surface also cut into strips. This
154 test was carried out at two temperature values: room temperature (22 °C) and at 40 °C.

155 The number of successful identifications allowed us to know if there was a significant
156 difference (statistical tables for triangular test [17]) between the laminate and the substrate
157 and, therefore, to choose the most odorant adhesives.

158 Once the most odorant adhesives for each group were selected, a descriptive analysis was
159 carried out to identify the sensory attributes (1g in colorless vials). This was done by a
160 team of 6 assessors, all of whom had previously carried out the triangular test with a high
161 success rate.

162

163 *2.4. Direct gas chromatography olfactometry (D-GC-O)*

164 The D-GC-O method was used to perform the representativeness test on the global odor
165 of the HS-SPME extracts in order to select the best extraction conditions. This recent
166 technique consists of connecting a deactivated capillary column between the injector and
167 sniffing port of a GC system in order to avoid chromatographic separation so that the
168 aroma compounds arrive simultaneously at the sniffing port. The equipment used was a
169 CP-3800 Varian equipped with the sniffing port ODO I supplied by SGE (Ringwood,
170 Australia) with a short capillary of untreated silica (20 cm x 0.32 mm i.d) from SGE
171 analytical science (Madrid, Spain).

172 The parameters of the D-GC-O device were as follows: injection system, splitless mode;
173 injector temperature, 250°C; oven temperature, 100°C; carrier gas, helium with a flow
174 rate of 1 mL/min.

175 For this assay, 5 grams of the adhesives (VAE_02, HM_01, starch, ACR and PVA) were
176 introduced into 20 mL vials. They were extracted by HS-SPME with different fibers and
177 different times. These extracts were introduced in successive sequence into the GC port
178 where the odorous compounds were thermally desorbed with the conditions above
179 described. The compounds arrived simultaneously at the sniffing port where the assessor
180 perceived, evaluated and compared the resulting global odor with the adhesive. This study
181 was repeated six times, each one with a different assessor. The best extraction conditions
182 (fiber and time) were selected.

183

184 2.5. GC-O-MS

185 2.5.1. Identification.

186 For the identification of the single odor compounds, the adhesives were firstly extracted
187 by two methodologies: HS-SPE and HS-SPME (conditions previously selected by D-GC-
188 O). The two extracts were then analyzed by GC-O-MS where the compounds were
189 separated in the chromatographic column and evaluated (retention time, intensity and
190 odor) at the sniffing port by six panelists. Simultaneous chemical identification was
191 achieved in the MS detector.

192 The equipment used was a CP-3800 Varian gas chromatograph system (Madrid, Spain)
193 connected to a Saturn 2000 series (Madrid, Spain) with an ion trap mass detector and
194 sniffing port ODO I supplied by SGE (Ringwood, Australia). Chromatographic
195 separations were carried out on a BP-20 (30 m x 0.25 mm x 0.25 μ m) from SGE analytical
196 science (Madrid, Spain). The oven temperature program was as follows; initial

197 temperature 40°C (5 min), heating rate of 10 °C/min to 220 °C, then held at 220°C for 10
198 minutes. Helium was used as carrier gas at 1 mL/min flow. The ionization was performed
199 by electronic impact and the ion trap temperature was 220 C. The electron multiplier
200 voltage was 1600V. Acquisition was carried out in SCAN mode (45-350 m/z).

201 For the analysis of HS-SPE extracts, 1µL of sample was injected in splitless mode and
202 the following injection conditions were used: initial temperature of 30 °C for 0.15 min
203 followed by a heating rate of 200 °C/min to 250 °C with 25 psi as pulse pressure. The split
204 valve was opened 2.5 min after injection.

205 For HS-SPME extraction, 5 grams of the adhesive (VAE_02, HM_01, starch, ACR and
206 PVA) were placed in a 20 mL vial each and the following extraction conditions were
207 applied: extraction temperature, 40°C; extraction time 15 min (previously selected by D-
208 GC-O as described above); DVB/CAR/PDMS fiber was used for the extraction of
209 VAE_02, starch, ACR and PVA adhesives and PDMS fiber was used for the HM_01
210 adhesive (previously selected by D-GC-O as described above). These extracts were
211 desorbed in the injection port at 250°C for 2 min with a splitless time of 2.5 min.

212

213 *2.5.2. Quantification.*

214 For the quantification of the odorous compounds, the adhesives (VAE_02, HM_01,
215 starch, ACR and PVA) were analyzed by HS-SPME coupled to GC-O-MS. A CP-3800
216 Varian gas chromatograph system (Madrid, Spain) connected to a Saturn 2000 series
217 (Madrid, Spain) with an ion trap mass detector was used under the same conditions as
218 those described above for the identification. The acquisition in this case was carried out
219 in SIM mode and the characteristic ions used for quantification purposes are shown in
220 Table 2.

221 The same conditions were used for the HS-SPME extraction of adhesives (VAE_02,
222 HM_01, starch, ACR and PVA) as for calibration curves with the standards.

223

224 *2.6. Extraction of volatile odorous compounds from adhesive*

225 The extraction of odorous compounds from the previously selected adhesives (VAE_02,
226 HM_01, starch, ACR and PVA) was carried out by the two methodologies described
227 below.

228

229 *2.6.1. Solid phase extraction (SPE) in headspace mode*

230 A standard SPE cartridge (0.8 cm internal diameter and 3 mL internal volume) filled with
231 400 mg of LiChrolut EN resins was first washed with 20 mL of dichloromethane and
232 dried with desiccant air (negative pressure of 0.6 bar, 10 min). The cartridge was placed
233 on the top of a bubbler flask containing about 50 mL of cured adhesive (54.85 grams of
234 VAE_02, 68.0 grams of HM_01, 55.50 grams of Starch, 60.05 g PVA and 61.60 g ACR)
235 at a constant temperature of 40 °C. A controlled gentle stream of nitrogen (500 mL/min)
236 was passed through the headspace for 140 min to carry all the volatile compounds out of
237 the flask to the SPE cartridge. The volatile compounds released by the adhesive in each
238 case were trapped in the cartridge containing the sorbent. After 140 min, the cartridge
239 was removed and dried by letting N₂ pass through it. The analytes were eluted with 3.2
240 mL of dichloromethane with 5% methanol. This process was used in previous works to
241 extract odorous compounds from wine samples [18-20]. The final extract was
242 concentrated under a stream of pure N₂ to a final volume of 500 µL. Five replicates of
243 each adhesive were used for subsequent identification.

244

245 *2.6.2. Extraction by solid phase microextraction (SPME) in headspace mode*

246 A rapid and simple technique was developed for evaluating the sensory quality of the
247 SPME extracts using the direct gas chromatography-olfactometry (D-GC-O) technique
248 described above. Different types of fibers and extraction times were tested. The assays
249 were as follows:

250 *Selection of appropriate fiber*

251 The first step was the selection of the most appropriate SPME fiber for each adhesive.
252 Four fibers with different polarity and thickness were tested:

- 253 • Divinylbenzene/carboxen/polydimethylsiloxane (DVB/CAR/PDMS) fiber of
254 50/30 µm
- 255 • Polydimethylsiloxane/divinylbenzene (PDMS/DVB) fiber of 65 µm
- 256 • Polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) fiber of 100 µm
- 257 • Polyacrylate (PA) fiber of 85 µm

258 The fiber selection was carried out by direct gas chromatography olfactometry (D-GC-
259 O) where four SPME extracts (four fibers studied for each adhesive at 40 °C and 15 min
260 of extraction) were introduced in successive sequences into the GC port without a
261 chromatographic column. As in these conditions there was no chromatographic
262 separation, the aroma compounds arrived all together at the sniffing port. Here, for each

263 SPME extract, a trained panel of six assessors perceived and evaluated the resulting
264 global odor, which was compared to the sample of adhesive. First, the assessors sniffed
265 the reference adhesive (5 grams) contained in a colorless vial. They memorized the odor
266 and compared it with the global aroma obtained at the sniffing port. The different extracts
267 were ranked according to their similarity to the reference using a 10 point scale ranging
268 from 0 (far from the reference) to 10 (close to the reference).

269 Selection of extraction time

270 Once the fiber was selected, the extraction time was optimized.

271 For this purpose, the adhesives were extracted with the fiber at different times (1, 5 and
272 25 min) and these different extracts were analyzed by D-GC-O applying the same criteria
273 as described above. The values more similar to the adhesive sample were compared to
274 the values previously obtained using the same fiber at 15 minutes of extraction. The
275 extraction time with the highest similarity value was chosen for further study.

276 Once the extraction conditions (fiber and time) were selected, the adhesives were
277 extracted by HS-SPME with the methodology described above. Five HS-SPME adhesive
278 extracts were used for subsequent identification.

279

280 *2.7. Identification of odorous compounds from the extract of adhesives*

281 To determine the odorous compounds in each adhesive, one microliter of HS-SPE extract
282 and HS-SPME extract obtained under the extraction conditions selected previously for
283 each adhesive were injected into the previously described GC-O-MS.

284 Six panelists were able to detect the individual odorous compounds eluted from the
285 chromatographic column and describe their odor notes. Besides, the intensity of these
286 odorous compounds was recorded using a scale from 1 to 3 units, where 1 corresponded
287 to the weakest odor (low intensity), 2 was a clear perception of odor (strong intensity)
288 and 3 corresponded to extremely strong intensity of odor. Fractional values were also
289 allowed. Afterwards, the modified frequency MF (%) was calculated to determine the
290 most important odorous compounds from each extract applying the following equation
291 [21]:

$$292 \quad MF(\%) = [F(\%) \times I(\%)]^{0.5}$$

293 where F(%) was the percentage of panelists who had detected the odorous compounds
294 and I(%) was the percentage of intensity calculated by the average of the values of
295 intensity given by all the panelists divided by three.

296 The odorous stimuli detected with a MF(%) higher than 50 were considered as
297 representing the most important compounds present in each adhesive extract. The
298 compounds found in more than one adhesive were also studied even if their MF(%) was
299 lower than 50.

300 Once the MF(%) was calculated and the most important odorous stimulus for each
301 extraction and each adhesive were selected, the identification was carried out. The
302 retention indexes of these compounds were calculated using a series of n-alkanes prepared
303 in hexane (C10 –C30) injected under the same chromatographic conditions. These
304 retention indexes and their organoleptic characteristics were compared to the compounds
305 with the same values found in the literature [8,22-29]. Additionally, mass spectral
306 matches obtained for unknown peaks from NIST and WILEY mass spectra libraries were
307 also used for identifying the compounds. Thus, a list of likely candidates was obtained
308 for each odorous stimulus found in each extract and in each adhesive.

309 Finally, the pure candidates prepared in dichloromethane were injected under the same
310 chromatographic conditions (GC-O-MS). To confirm the identification, these candidates
311 had to match the unknown odorous compounds in terms of their retention indexes, odor
312 characteristic and the mass spectrum.

313

314 *2.8. Determination of the initial concentration profile (CP₀) of odorous compounds from*
315 *adhesives*

316 Once the odorous compounds extracted for each adhesive were identified, their initial
317 concentrations were calculated. For this purpose, the adhesives (VAE_02, HM_01,
318 starch, ACR and PVA) were analyzed by HS-SPME coupled to GC-O-MS (15 min and
319 PDMS fiber for HM_01 and DVB/CAR/PDMS for the other adhesives). The HS-SPME
320 extraction for the quantification proved to be a fast, very sensitive and free-solvent
321 technique.

322 Before the initial concentrations were calculated, a study was carried out to avoid the
323 matrix effect for quantification in the water based adhesives (VAE_02, Starch, PVA and
324 ACR). For this purpose, the adhesives were diluted in different proportions (1, 5, 10, 50,
325 100 and 200) and analyzed with DVB/CAR/PDMS fiber by HS-SPME-GC-O-MS. The

326 signal obtained was compared with that obtained when the adhesives were diluted in the
327 same proportions and spiked with the previously identified compounds. The increase in
328 the signal was compared with the signal obtained when 100% water samples were spiked
329 at the same concentration level. The dilution factor was selected on the basis of the
330 minimum water dilution obtained with minimum matrix effects and maximum sensitivity
331 of each sample for achieving recoveries over 90% for all odorous compounds[4].

332 For this assay, aliquots of 5 g of each solution were placed in headspace vials and 10 μ L
333 of solution A were added as an internal standard.

334 After that, the CP_0 was calculated. For building the calibration curves, solutions of
335 different concentrations of the identified compounds were prepared in purified water.
336 Aliquots of 5 mL of each solution were placed in headspace vials and 10 μ L of solution
337 A were added as internal standard. Three replicates of each sample were prepared and
338 analyzed with DVB/CAR/PDMS by HS-SPME-GC-O-MS.

339 The initial concentration of the HM_01 adhesive was determined in another way, because
340 this adhesive was solid at room temperature. In this case, to determine the CP_0 a standard
341 addition procedure was carried out. For this purpose, 5 grams of the pure adhesive were
342 heated at 160 °C (to be cured) and, once melted, 10 μ L of solution containing different
343 concentrations of the compounds identified for this adhesive and also 10 μ L of solution
344 A as an internal standard were spiked. Three replicates of each sample were prepared and
345 analyzed with PDMS (previously selected for this adhesive) by HS-SPME-GC-O-MS.

346

347 **3. Results and discussion**

348

349 The aim of this work was to identify and quantify the odorous compounds in five different
350 types of adhesives (HM, VAE, starch, PVA and ACR). As several HM and VAE
351 adhesives were available, firstly the most odorant adhesives of each type were selected
352 by a triangular test. Once these adhesives were selected, they (HM_01, VAE_02, starch,
353 PVA and ACR) were extracted by two techniques (HS-SPE and HS-SPME) in order to
354 obtain the highest number of odorous compounds. Previous to the identification, the
355 conditions of HS-SPME extraction (fiber and time) for each adhesive were selected by
356 D-GC-O. After that, they were identified by GC-O-MS where six panelists evaluated their
357 time of retention, odor and intensity, and they were confirmed by the pure standard. Once
358 the identification was carried out, their initial concentration in the adhesive was calculated
359 by HS-SPME-GC-O-MS.

360

361

362 *3.1. Selection of the most odorant adhesive for each type of adhesives and their sensory*
363 *analysis*

364 Firstly, the most odorous adhesive within each group of hotmelt and VAE adhesives was
365 selected through a triangular test.

366 For the adhesives VAE_01, VAE_02 and VAE_03, there were no significant differences
367 between the laminate (Lam_01, Lam_02 and Lam_03 respectively) and their substrates
368 at room temperature. However, significant differences were found at 40 °C, for the
369 Lam_01 ($p < 0.4$), Lam_02 ($p < 0.01$) and Lam_03 ($p < 0.01$), so the adhesives VAE_02 and
370 VAE_03 were the most odorous within the group. However, VAE_02 was selected
371 because its success rate in the triangular test was higher at both temperatures (room and
372 40 °C) than for the adhesive VAE_03 (13 successes compared to 12, respectively, at
373 40°C).

374 The same occurred for the HM adhesives where the differences between the substrate and
375 the laminate were not found at room temperature, while at 40 °C significant differences
376 for the adhesives Lam_04 ($p < 0.001$), Lam_05 ($p < 0.05$) and Lam_06 ($p < 0.05$) were
377 found. Therefore, the adhesive HM_01 was selected for the study.

378 Once the VAE_02 and HM_01 were selected as the most odorous adhesives within each
379 type, a qualitative descriptive analysis was carried out for all the adhesives. The sensory
380 attributes were assessed. White glue, plastic, pungent and paint odor were found for the
381 adhesive VAE_02. For the adhesive HM_01, rubber tire, woody, depilatory wax, phenolic
382 and leather odors were described. For the starch adhesive, rancid, ferment, white glue and
383 paint odor were assigned. For the PVA adhesive, the odor attributed was a very pungent
384 odor like vinegar and, finally, for the ACR adhesive moss, humidity and camphor were
385 assigned as the main sensory properties.

386

387 *3.2. Extraction by head space solid phase microextraction*

388 Before carrying out the identification, the conditions for HS-SPME extraction were
389 optimized.

390 *Selection of the appropriate SPME fiber*

391 Figure 1 shows the results of the similarity scale calculated as the average similarity
392 values between the four SPME global odors with respect to the adhesive of reference

393 given by the different panelists by D-GC-O. The highest similarity values were between
394 6.3 and 8.4.

395 For the HM_01 adhesive, the most representative extracts were obtained from the PDMS,
396 PDMS/DVB and DVB/CAR/PDMS fibers (similarity values of 6.3, 5.5 and 4.5,
397 respectively). Thus, PA fiber (polar phase) provided the worst representative extract
398 whose similarity value was significantly lower. The PDMS fiber was selected because it
399 gave the highest similarity value. This is consistent with findings in a previous work to
400 extract the volatile migrant compounds from hotmelt adhesives [3] in which PDMS
401 showed the best performance. This fiber extracts the compounds of low polarity, which
402 could be the unknown odorous compounds.

403 For the VAE_02, the optimum SPME fiber that provided the highest odor extract was the
404 DVB/CAR/PDMS, whose value was significantly higher. For the rest of the fibers, the
405 similarity values were below the score of 2.3. The same trend was found for starch and
406 PVA adhesives for which clearly the best extract was obtained by the DVB/CAR/PDMS
407 fiber (6.8 and 8.4, respectively). However, for the ACR adhesive the most representative
408 extracts were obtained by the DVB/CAR/PDMS and PDMS fibers. DVB/CAR/PDMS
409 was selected due to its higher similarity value.

410 The DVB/CAR/PDMS fiber, which has a structure with micropores, mainly extracted the
411 low molecular weight compounds. These could be the odorous compounds and for this
412 reason this proved to be the best fiber in most cases.

413 Summarizing, the optimum fibers selected were the PDMS fiber for the HM_01 adhesive
414 and the DVB/CAR/PDMS for the rest of the adhesives.

415

416 Selection of extraction time

417 Once the fiber for each adhesive was selected, the extraction time was optimized. Figure
418 2 shows the average similarity values between the extracts and the reference sample for
419 different extraction times. For all the adhesives, there were significant differences
420 between 1 and 5 minutes versus 15 and 25 min. Longer extraction times achieved higher
421 scores (similarity ranges from 5.7 to 8.5) than short extraction times (rate ranges from 1.2
422 to 4.6). As significant differences were not obtained between 15 and 25 minutes of
423 extraction, 15 minutes was the selected extraction time.

424

425 *3.3. Identification of odorous compounds from the adhesives extracted by HS-SPE and*
426 *HS-SPME coupled to GC-O-MS*

427 Figures 3, 4, 5, 6 and 7 show the chromatograms of HM_01, VAE_02, starch, PVA, and
428 ACR adhesives, respectively, analyzed by GC-O-MS and extracted by HS-SPE or HS-
429 SPME. The compounds with odor characteristics are indicated in the figures with
430 numbers ordered by their retention index (Table 1). Thirty three compounds detected had
431 characteristic odors either with $MF(\%) > 50$ or $MF(\%) < 50$, but they were all selected
432 because they were found in more than one adhesive using the same extraction technique.
433 Table 1 shows the odor compounds identified for each adhesive (with their retention
434 indexes) and their $MF(\%)$ obtained for each extraction technique. Some compounds found
435 in these adhesives showed a higher $MF(\%)$ when they were extracted by the HS-SPE
436 technique than by HS-SPME, such as p-xylene detected in the VAE adhesive, with values
437 of $MF(\%)$ from 65.3% to 50.3%. By contrast, 1-octanol found in the PVA adhesive
438 showed values of $MF(\%)$ higher with the HS-SPME technique than with HS-SPE
439 Some compounds were detected only by one extraction technique, which emphasizes the
440 importance of using two extraction techniques. These can be seen as complementary
441 techniques for identification in this case. For example, some compounds whose retention
442 indexes were lower than 1092 (where the solvent was detected) were only detected by the
443 HS-SPME extract, because this technique is solventless and thus no solvent delay is
444 required in MS. The solvent prevents the analyst from sniffing the odorous compounds
445 when the SPE extracts are directly injected.

446 Using two complementary extraction techniques, the number of odorous compounds
447 detected increased and consequently the list of possible migrant compounds to food also
448 increased.

449 The compounds identified were several acids such as acetic, propanoic and butyric acid,
450 which provided common organoleptic characteristics to the adhesives such as sour,
451 vinegar, rancid and cheese aromas. Ester compounds such as methyl butyrate with cheese
452 aroma and allyl and methyl benzoate with sweet aroma were also identified. Aldehyde
453 compounds such as hexanal and nonanal with grass and green aromas were also found in
454 several adhesives, or alcohol compounds such as cyclohexanol and 1-butanol with
455 camphor and medicine aromas.

456 In the HM_01 adhesive, odor descriptors such as pine, herb and woody were repeated,
457 which could be produced by calamenene and longifolene compounds. These compounds
458 are present in the essential oils coming from the resin used for the manufacture of this
459 kind of adhesive [3,26-28]. Some of the sensory attributes described above for this
460 adhesive were depilatory wax or woody, which could come from these compounds.

461 In the VAE_02, three compounds, p-xylene (sweet), benzaldehyde (bitter almond) and
462 one unknown compound with a plastic odor at RI 1797 were found which were not present
463 in the rest of the adhesives. This latter compound could be responsible for the plastic
464 aroma found by the assessors in the descriptive analysis. Two other sensory attributes
465 were white glue and pungent, which could come from acetic acid. Toluene could be
466 responsible for the paint attribute described above.

467 In the starch adhesive, three compounds (paraldehyde, propanoic acid and allyl benzoate)
468 were found which did not appear in the other adhesives. The propanoic acid compound
469 and the higher MF(%) of butyric acid may be responsible for the rancid aroma found by
470 the descriptive analysis. The aromas of white glue and paint found in this adhesive could
471 also come from acetic acid and toluene, respectively.

472 In the PVA adhesive, the most important sensory attribute described above was the
473 vinegar odor, which could come from acetic acid, whose MF(%) was the highest of the
474 set of adhesives by both extraction techniques.

475 In the ACR adhesive, camphor (camphor), 1-octanol (mushroom, moss) and one
476 unknown compound with a mushroom odor at RI 1216 were found which were not
477 present in the rest of the adhesives. These could be responsible for the camphor, moss and
478 humidity aromas found by the assessors in the descriptive analysis.

479

480 *3.4. The initial concentration profile, CP_0 , of the odor compounds in the adhesives*

481 Once the odorous compounds were identified, their initial concentrations were calculated.
482 These assays were carried out by HS-SPME-GC-O-MS.

483 Previously, the dilution factor was selected in order to minimize the matrix effects and to
484 obtain the maximum sensitivity in each adhesive (VAE_02, starch, ACR and PVA). To
485 achieve recoveries over 90% for all the odor compounds, the adhesives were water diluted
486 1/100 (w/w).

487 To build the calibration curve, the compounds found for these adhesives were spiked in
488 pure water at different concentrations. Analytical parameters of the HS-SPME-GC-O-MS
489 (DVB/CAR/PDMS fiber) method and the ions used for their quantification are shown in
490 Table 2. Good results were obtained in terms of linearity, limits of detection (LOD) and
491 reproducibility. LOD values were between 0.03 ng/g (naphthalene) and 5.02
492 micrograms/g (butyric acid). RSD values were between 2.03 and 15.1%.

493 To quantify the compounds found in the HM_01 (1-butanol, p-cymene, nonanal, acetic
494 acid and naphthalene), a standard addition procedure was carried out. The analytical

495 parameters of the HS-SPME-GC-O-MS (PDMS fiber) method and the ions used for their
496 quantification are also shown in Table 2. Again, good results were obtained in terms of
497 linearity. RSD values were between 6.8 and 14.2%.

498 Due to the difficulty in finding the standards for longifolene, calamenene and methyl
499 butyrate, these were quantified using naphthalene as a standard for longifolene and
500 calamenene, and butyric acid to quantify methyl butyrate.

501 The concentrations of the identified odor compounds, expressed as ng of compound per
502 g of adhesive, are shown in Table 2. As would be expected, there is a clear relationship
503 between the concentration and the MF(%) for each compound found. For instance, the
504 concentration of toluene, whose MF(%) increased depending on the type of adhesive,
505 from 13.6 in starch adhesive to 68.3 in VAE_02 adhesive, increased from 0.07 to 277
506 ng/g adhesive, as Table 1 shows. The same tendency was observed for 1-butanol
507 identified in all the adhesives. Its MF(%) increased from 9.2 to 100, depending on the
508 type of adhesive, increasing its concentration from < 8810 to 60.300 ng of compound per
509 g of adhesive.

510 Comparing different compounds with the same MF(%), the relationship between the
511 MF(%) and the concentration disappeared since compounds with similar MF(%) had
512 different concentrations. For example, acetic and butyric acids had similar MF(%) in the
513 Starch adhesive and VAE_02 for the SPE extract (65.0 and 65.3, respectively, as shown
514 in Table 1) while their concentrations were totally different with values of 52600 and
515 <16700 ng/g, respectively, as shown in Table 2. This fact can be explained by their
516 different odor thresholds. While acetic acid had 0.363 (mg/m³) according to Devos et al.
517 or 0.145 (mg/m³) according to SchiMFFan et al [30], the butyric acid threshold is 0.0145
518 (mg/m³) according to Devos et al. or 0.00389 (mg/m³) according to SchiMFFan et al
519 [30,31]. This means that butyric acid will be better perceived by the human nose than
520 acetic acid as its odor threshold is lower, and therefore with a lower concentration its
521 MF(%) will be higher.

522 The most abundant compound in all the adhesives was acetic acid. Its concentration
523 ranged from 22900 to 8930000 ng/g adhesive depending on the type of adhesive. The
524 PVA adhesive had the highest concentration, this being consistent with the attributes of
525 the assessors who had assigned pungent and vinegar odors in the sensory analysis. The
526 other major odorous compounds were p-cymene (28300 ng/g) in the HM_01 adhesive,
527 ethyl acetate (464000 ng/g) and 1-butanol (60300 ng/g) for the PVA adhesive, and methyl

528 methacrylate (56200 ng/g), 2-ethylhexyl acetate (68500 ng/g) and 2-ethyl-1-hexanol
529 (514000 ng/g) for the ACR adhesive.

530

531 **Conclusion**

532 The odorous compounds from adhesives (hotmelt, vinyl acetate ethylene, starch,
533 polyvinyl acetate and acrylic) commonly used in food packaging materials have been
534 identified and quantified. Two extracts of these adhesives obtained by two different
535 methodologies, HS-SPE and HS-SPME (the type of fiber and extraction time being
536 optimized for each adhesive by a simple and rapid D-GC-O method) have been analyzed
537 by the GC-O-MS method. This has proved to be a useful and reliable tool to identify a
538 great number of odorous compounds in these adhesives. Thirty three compounds with
539 characteristic odors were identified; some of them, such as butyric acid, acetic acid,
540 methyl butyrate, 1-butanol and nonanal, were present in most of the adhesives. The most
541 abundant compound was acetic acid with a concentration range between 22900-8930000
542 ng/g with a sour and vinegar aroma. We can conclude that the two extraction
543 methodologies are complementary, as several compounds were trapped either in the SPE
544 cartridge or in the SPME fiber but not in both. Besides, this study emphasizes the
545 importance of identifying a large number of the chemical compounds responsible for off-
546 flavors coming from adhesives. This leads to a possible way forward for adhesive
547 companies to reformulate and replace these odorous compounds by other odorless
548 compounds or to reduce their concentrations in order to avoid their migration into food
549 and the consequent undesirable organoleptic changes.

550

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556

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Table 1: Identified odorous compounds with its retention index (RI) and its odor description perceived by the different assessors. Its modified frequency (%MF) by HS-SPE and HS-SPME extraction in five different types of adhesives (HM_01, VAE_02, Starch, PVA and ACR)

N	RI	Compound	Odor description	%MF (HM_01)		%MF (VAE_02)		%MF (Starch)		%MF (PVA)		%MF (ACR)	
				SPE	SPME	SPE	SPME	SPE	SPME	SPE	SPME	SPE	SPME
1	907	Ethyl acetate	Fruity, sweet								54.4		
2	1005	No identified (n.i)	Pungent		50.3								
3	1022	Methyl methacrylate	Sharp fruity										81.6
4	1035	Toluene	Paint				68.3		13.6				
5	1077	Hexanal	Grass, fat						51.8		64.5		
6	1092	Paraldehyde	Pungent, disagreeable						53.6				
7	1098	P-xylene	Sweet			65.3	50.3						
8	1120	Butyl propanoate	Earthy, sweet										64.5
9	1168	1-butanol	Medicine		9.2		16.3		28.9	54.9	100	57.7	
10	1170	Butyl acrylate	Pungent fruit						50.9				100
11	1216	N.i	Mushroom									84.7	
12	1241	Styrene	Gasoline, balsamic									52.7	59.7
13	1280	P-cymene	Gasoline, solvent	52.6									

14	1285	2-octanone	Herb, resin										85.0
15	1359	1-hexanol	Resin, green			54.0				83.3			
16	1382	2-ethylhexyl acetate	Sharp										76.42
17	1400	Nonanal	Fresh, green	58.3		44.7		33.2					
18	1411	Cyclohexanol	Camphor					51.0				57.7	
19	1427	N.i	Disagreeable, woody	50.9		78.3							
20	1466	Acetic acid	Sour, like vinegar	62.4	68.9	76.1	79.1	65.0	69.3	100	100	79.9	62.3
21	1487	2-ethyl-1-hexanol	Green										100
22	1491	Camphor	camphor										64.5
23	1536	Propanoic acid	Rancid					50.2					
24	1539	Benzaldehyde	Bitter almond			53.8	51.5						
25	1553	1-octanol	moss, mushroom									72.7	85.0
26	1570	Longifolene	Woody , pine	54.0		50.0							
27	1626	Butyric acid	Rancid, cheese	45.3		65.3		71.4		40.8		60.9	
28	1627	Methyl benzoate	Aromatic, sweet					31.2		43.0			
29	1689	Methyl butyrate	Cheese	37.4		38.2		35.2					
30	1785	Naphthalene	Tar, mothball	47.3						31.5		52.7	
31	1797	N.i	Plastic, glue			50.0							

32	1823	Allyl benzoate	Sweet, floral			50.2	59.1
33	1835	Calamenene	Herb spice	55.3	51.1		

Table 2: Initial concentration profile for the identified odorous compounds, CP_o expressed as ng of compound per g de adhesive for each adhesive, the analytical parameters of the HS-SPME-GC-O-MS method (with DVB/CAR/PDMS fiber and with PDMS fiber annotated by *)

Compounds	Quant. ion	HM_01 ng/gadh	VAE_02 ng/gadh	Starch ng/gadh	PVA ng/gadh	ACR ng/gadh	Equation	R ²	Linear range (ng/g)	LOD (ng/g)	LOQ (ng/g)	RSD (%)
Ethyl acetate	43				464000		$y=0.017x+0.049$	0.991	450-49600	135	450	8.35
Methyl methacrylate	69					56200	$y=1.928x+0.005$	0.999	5.69-1070	1.71	5.69	6.57
Toluene	91		277	0.07			$y=70.06x+0.228$	0.999	0.06-106	0.05	0.06	5.17
Hexanal	44			277	1200		$y=5.566+0.034$	0.994	4.87-111	1.46	4.87	11.3
Paraldehyde	45			175			$y=0.101x+0.019$	0.998	27.8-1920	8.35	27.8	7.38
P-xylene	91		425				$y=451.1x+0.124$	0.997	0.26-99.3	0.07	0.26	2.03
Butyl propanoate	57					122	$y=65.53x+0.224$	0.998	2.31-1140	0.71	2.31	13.9
1-butanol	56		<LOQ	<LOQ	60300	8950	$y=0.002x+0.015$	0.997	8810-95600	2640	8810	9.74
1-butanol*	56	885					$y=0.0008x+0.007^*$	0.998				8.77
Butyl acrylate	55			11.5		8230	$y=92.22x+0.037$	0.998	0.88-88.1	0.26	0.88	14.6
Styrene	104					445	$y=459.2x+0.103$	0.999	0.36-86.3	0.11	0.36	7.46
P-cymene	119						$y=4.268x-0.305$	0.994	0.58-4250	0.17	0.58	5.56
P-cymene*	119	28300					$y=0.0053x+0.1315^*$	0.989				8.77
2-octanone	43				326		$y=59.56x-0.031$	0.999	0.37-87.2	0.11	0.37	8.89

1-hexanol	56		7480			11500		$y=0.643x-0.009$	0.991	93.8-24500	28.2	93.8	5.33
2-ethylhexyl acetate	43						68500	$y=208.3x-0.029$	0.999	0.29-89.7	0.09	0.29	4.33
Nonanal	57		405	158				$y=37.02x-0.008$	0.994	2.12-193	0.64	2.12	13.6
Nonanal*	57	2630						$y=0.0217x+0.2714^*$	0.985				6.88
Cyclohexanol	57		4420			4390		$y=0.087x+0.002$	0.997	91.7-1080	27.5	91.7	15.1
Acetic acid	43		429000	52600	8930000	72700		$y=0.041x+0.012$	0.997	130-9320	38.8	130	14.6
Acetic acid*	43	22900						$y=0.033x+0.0612^*$	0.989				12.3
2-ethyl-1-hexanol	57						514000	$y=6.680x+0.259$	0.999	9.93-894	2.98	9.93	14.6
Camphor	95						6080	$y=0.698x-0.052$	0.991	2.98-1030	0.99	2.98	6.99
Propanoic acid	74			<LOQ				$y=0.007x+0.014$	0.984	2410-95900	724	2410	3.53
Benzaldehyde	106		6390					$y=4.927x-0.054$	0.999	31.2-1020	9.35	31.2	13.2
1-octanol	56						1350	$y=3.141x-0.026$	0.999	19.1-954	5.75	19.1	9.06
Longifolene ^a	161	1430											
Butyric acid	60	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ		$y=0.041-0.147$	0.996	16700-99100	5020	16700	12.1
Methyl benzoate	105		1810	6941				$y=17.06x-0.119$	0.997	9.85-1150	2.96	9.85	2.85
Methyl butyrate ^b	43	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ									
Naphthalene	128	2510		429				$y=410.6x+0.046$	0.998	0.10-98.5	0.03	0.10	12.2
Naphthalene*	128							$y=0.6104x+1.7662^*$	0.985				4.30

Allyl benzoate	105		4150		$y=17.27x-0.396$	0.997	2.67-1120	0.80	2.67	3.93
Calamenene ^a	159	1340								

* Standard addition

^a Quantified with naphthalene* as standard

^b Quantified with butyric acid as standard

Figure 1: Similarity rates obtained with several SPME fibers by sensory panel of 6 assessors; the scale ranges from 0 (far from the reference) to 10 (close to the reference)

Figure 2: Similarity rates obtained with different extraction times in SPME samples by sensory panel of 6 assessors; the scale ranges from 0 (far from the reference) to 10 (close to the reference)

Figure 3: Chromatogram of the HM_01 adhesive analyzed by HS-SPE-GC-MS (on the top) and HS-SPME-GC-MS using a PDMS fiber (on the bottom)

Figure 4: Chromatogram of the VAE_02 adhesive analyzed by HS-SPE-GC-MS (on the top) and HS-SPME-GC-MS using a DVB/CAR/PDMS fiber (on the bottom)

Figure 5: Chromatogram of starch adhesive analyzed by HS-SPE-GC-MS (on the top) and HS-SPME-GC-MS using a DVB/CAR/PDMS fiber (on the bottom)

Figure 6: Chromatogram of the PVA adhesive analyzed by HS-SPE-GC-MS (on the top) and HS-SPME-GC-MS using a DVB/CAR/PDMS fiber (on the bottom)

Figure 7: Chromatogram of the ACR adhesive analyzed by HS-SPE-GC-MS (on the top) and HS-SPME-GC-MS using a DVB/CAR/PDMS fiber (on the bottom)